

LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECT THE CATEGORY OF SPACE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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Abstract; Linguistic aspect of the category of space in English and Uzbek languages is devoted to consideration of linguistic and cognitive aspects. The selection of this specific problem as a research subject is due to the insufficient development of the cultural studies plan of the translation. Although translation studies emphasizes the need to take into account the influence of culture on translation, no serious theoretical research has been conducted in this direction so far.

Keywords; Linguistic, categorical, culturological, language culture, depicted culture,

We propose a cultural concept of translation of the linguistic and cultural aspect of the category of space in English and Uzbek languages, according to which the uniqueness of culture is not unambiguously manifested in the translated texts, but at least in two ways. To make our point more concise, it can be described as "culture in language". By this we mean a special linguistic representation of the world, that is, a unique representation of reality in language. This mediator includes cultural factors, that is, specific cognitive-semantic structures that represent the uniqueness of the thinking structures of representatives of different cultures.

In accordance with the above-mentioned opinion, we will complicate it with another topic, which we call "culture described by language". This concept and term refers to cultural symbols, the way symbols are manifested in the content of texts. In this regard, it is important to understand culture as a set of material and spiritual characteristics that determine the specific characteristics of the organization of people's thinking, social and domestic life. The scientific innovation of this translation concept is that translation is considered as a cultural phenomenon combining factors of two levels (cognitive-semantic and real-cultural).

The following cultural frames can be activated when describing the person in English expressions: personal, personal - singular, personal generalization, personal-animistic, physical-part together with animistic. In Uzbek, they are related to: story; collegial; personal generalization; personal - unique; generalizing-uncertain; personal integration.

At the same time, there is a general trend in the ways of expressing the person in English culture, which manifests itself in the form of a larger person in English!

description. On the contrary, the Uzbek language shows a desire to be a collective (collegial) representative of the "actors" of the situation.

In accordance with our opinion presented above, translation problems can be considered from two aspects - cognitive-semantic and cultural. In our view, text-to-text transfer in all respects represents a transfer from one language to another (source language to target language) as well as from one culture to another (source culture to target language).

Analysis of language material with "ordinary" cultural features has shown that some of them can be preserved in translation (for example, the sign of banknotes). However, in most cases, cultural and pragmatic adaptation occurs in the following directions: the use of a sign in the translation with a wider meaning than the sign in the original; "ignore" the translation of the uninformative sign for the receiver of Uzbek culture; explaining a foreign cultural symbol in translation; selects an Uzbek cultural characteristic that roughly corresponds to an English cultural sign.

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